

Gender Roles Demystified in F. Sionil Jose's "The Feet of Juan Bacnang"

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Introduction

Gender is not something that we are born with; gender is what we are socialized into. It is something that is imposed to us by institutions of power like family, school, and the church. Almost all cultures associate gender with sex, but there is a big difference. Sex is strictly biological, while gender is everything else aside from the biological aspect; it is behavior, emotional, and social characteristics attributed to men and women. Gender, then, is dictated upon us and culture is the basis of our behavior. Some cultures have women as sexual aggressors, and in others, women as construction workers. This proves that gender is something fluid and that both men and women are not boxed into the stereotype. This paper would focus on how gender roles are demystified in F. Sionil Jose's "The Feet of Juan Bacnang," no matter how subtle they may be. This paper would also note some important observations on nomenclature and the protagonist vis-à-vis the ethno-epic hero.

Analysis and Discussion

In F. Sionil Jose's "The Feet of Juan Bacnang," we see the character of Juan dela Cruz IV as a sexual predator. His first sexual experience was with his childhood love, Aning. Even as a child, Juan Bacnang already proved himself hungry for sex, and this does coincide with the gender role of men being "superior." Men are expected to be sexually aggressive and polygamous, and Juan Bacnang embodies this description, even his father Juan dela Cruz III and The Leader. All three were described to have slept with many women in order for them to "plant the seed," and their perception of women is that "they do not carry the seed." They are the earth on which the seed is planted. That is their function, that is what God created them for" (140). The statement used God, which makes it seem like it is gospel truth – something beyond knowledge because God is already the one pointing out women's purpose, even when it is not a fact. On the one hand, we see these men's virility and hunger in bed and for power. On the other hand, we see women like Aning and Bibi, who are characters totally in control of their bodies. In Helene Cixous' *The Laugh of the Medusa*, she mentions that.

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...because you didn't go all the way; or because you wrote, irresistibly, as when we would masturbate in secret, not to go further, but to attenuate the tension a bit, just enough to take the edge off. And then, as soon as we come, we go and make ourselves feel guilty – so as to be forgiven; or to forget, to bury it until the next time (2041).

After being raped by Juan Bacnang, Aning worked at The Lika, a sex emporium, as a prostitute with an estimate of servicing about ten men per day. At first, we may see Aning destroyed and depressed with her life because she sees herself as trash, seeing herself not worthy for anyone because she is not sexually modest. It does coincide with the lines that Cixous mentioned – guilt was felt by Aning while working at the Lika. Later on, we realize that Aning actually utilized her body in order to earn more money which allowed her to pay for her sister's tuition. In this part, we know that Aning has already used her body to her advantage and moved away from what society dictates that a woman must only have one sexual partner. Another character that has veered away from sexual modesty is Bibi, and we can see that in the lines of the novel.

Johnny's lovemaking was her greatest rapture, the very reason, although this was never clear to her, why all thoughts of partying, that dizzying social whirl, had slowly drifted away from her. Whenever she could, she dragged Johnny to the bedroom where, with all those mirrors around them, she clung to him, worshipped his body which stirred in her marrow-deep quivering, a warm tingling as she received him in complete abandon. She could spend the whole night in his embrace, lulled into a euphoric hypnotic state, as if she were lifted from this mundane world into that cosmic ether where there was only all-encompassing happiness (111-112).

In the following statements, Bibi is seen as a woman who is sexually aggressive, someone who would choose to lay on bed and play with fire with her husband, rather than attend a party. Women have been "turned away from our bodies, shamefully taught to ignore them, to strike them with that stupid sexual modesty; we've been made victims of the old fool's game: each one will love the other sex" (Cixous 2049). According to Filipino culture, women are not supposedly the ones initiating the act, more so, they are the passive characters who would just agree to their husbands. The vagina is hidden, biologically speaking, as compared to the penis that is why she should not be more aggressive than men. Women are expected to be like Maria Clara and Virgin Mary, because we have been brainwashed that this is the only proper way a woman should act. Bibi moves away from the stereotype that women are supposedly meek and mild when it comes to matters like sex.

In the novel, one ancient practice was also explained which is the embodiment of a “stupid sexual modesty.” In the old days, so he learned from the older men, it was the practice in the North for the bride to hang on her window the white blanket used on her bridal night, the specks of red – her blood – on it to show to every passerby that sacred ligament had, indeed, been intact – the bride’s ultimate homage to her husband (101). This practice forces women to be chaste in order to gift their virginity to their future husband. If in case a woman is raped, she is still going to be blamed by society because it would appear that she seduced the man to do it. Nonetheless, the woman is shamed if she is not able to follow the said practice – she will be seen as an unclean being, a whore for the rest of her life; something that even her future child would hear off because of the gossip in town.

Women were perceived to be “naturally” subordinate to men, no questions whatsoever. Eleonor Dionisio mentions that “in reality, gender limits both men and women. This limitation means more than mere gender discrimination: the gender system supports and interacts with other social systems which keep the majority of people, women and men, from achieving full and dignified lives” (14). Gender subordination is very much present in Philippine politics and the corporate world. More men hold higher offices than women, whether it be in the government or in the corporate world. Women are not properly represented in the government, which is why there is not much focus on issues concerning them like a good child support system in the Philippines; anything that is an issue of a woman is seen as a side issue, something of less importance. In the novel, we can see how a male child is treated as a precious gem.

In the recent past the oldest son became the sole inheritor of the family’s wealth, where baby girls were considered bad luck and were killed at birth – “weeding,” they called it in the East. But not male children – they were heaven sent, prizes to be valued, for they will not only perpetuate the seed, they will also provide leaders of a clan, the crown prince, the king, the sultan (41).

This only male child is trained and honed to be another politician and CEO. No matter how many Juan dela Cruz III’s daughters are, “six girls by his legitimate wife, and two dozen more by other women” (41), his happiness cannot be compared for when he learned that Juan Bacnang is his son – the rightful heir to the throne, after countless times of trying to have a son. When Juan dela Cruz IV’s twins were born, it was bluntly mentioned in the novel that “Juan already favored his son over his twin, a girl, who might grow up to be flighty and incapable of preserving what he had built because she is a woman, prone to the weaknesses of her sex” (125). We see how evident it is that a male child is definitely patronized as compared to the female children, although the female children were not weeded out, the point is that they were not given the chance to handle the massive dela Cruz empire. Liwliwa, Juan dela Cruz IV’s daughter, already has a set future that she would not be the one handling the future of the dela Cruz domain because she is “just a woman,” someone not capable of doing what men can do. Since women are seen as “home-makers,” their position in the government are those similar to what they do at home; posts at the Department of Social Welfare and Development is one of the branches of government where women reign.

Gender subordination is oftentimes associated to women being submissive to men; women being too dependent of men because they are the providers. Women actually play an important role behind the prowess presented by the men because the “extent of men’s public role is made possible by the unacknowledged support of women’s work in the household, and sometimes in the public sphere as well” (Dionisio 18). If men are not given this support, their success as public officials may suffer grievously. In the novel, all women play vital roles in the lives of the men in order for them to function. Agnes plays a vital role as the private secretary of Juan dela Cruz III and a confidante of Juan dela Cruz IV. Agnes is not just any secretary, she is a private secretary and the term “private” entails that there are confidential matters that Agnes attends to, especially because she is part of the family. When Juan dela Cruz III died, Juan Bacnang leaned on Agnes, “with her training and knowledge of many intricate labyrinths in their domain, stood by him, ready to fight for him” (126). Agnes was the light of Juan dela Cruz IV into the ins and outs of their empire, and without Agnes, Sunny Johnny might not be as sunny as he is. Another strong character that is often overlooked, but has a lot of heart in the story is Tecla, Juan Bacnang’s mother. The mother’s death urged Juan Bacnang to fix the whole town of Nalipatan:

To the aide, Johnny said that the tombs be cemented and marked with marble crosses, that the old house be repaired, restored to its original shape, and that a much bigger residence be built close to it – a bungalow with three rooms where he and the family could stay when they visited. The road to Nalipatan should be widened and asphalted, and electricity must now be brought to the barrio” (60).

Love for the mother, even the guilt felt by Juan Bacnang for his absence during the times that his mother was dying, was the trigger that pushed him to make changes in the barrio. He used his money and power in order to act upon what she wanted to happen.

Gender subordination in the novel is very much evident because the heads of the company are dominated by men. But there is a great exchange of power between the roles of the women presented in the story. Liwliwa, the female offspring of Juan dela Cruz IV, served as Anos’ stronghold. The twins, being twins, had no secrets between them. Liw knew all about her brother’s escapades with Jessica and the money he gave to Jessica. In turn, Anos also knew about the attachment of Liw to Jimmy, the driver’s son. Liw was the sole person who understood what Anos was feeling, although not entirely, Liw knew how Anos was hurt when Jessica died. It may be implied that it was their father, Juan dela Cruz IV, who was behind the idea of throwing acid into Jessica’s face which rendered her depressed, later on, commit suicide. This is probably what Anos tried to say in his suicide note: “Dear Papa – Please forgive me. I cannot live with what I have lost and with what I have discovered” (172). Anos probably figured out that it was his father’s doing and he would not want to be like his father, thus ending his own life. After this incident, Juan dela Cruz IV sent Jimmy’s family away, in order to be apart from Liw. After, Liw’s death, it can be seen that Liw has a stronger grip at life, than Anos. Both were robbed of their partners, but it was Anos who took his own life, not willing to face whatever happens in the future.

Liwliwa unfortunately died because of what seemed like an accident, but nonetheless, she had more time facing the challenges of life; Liw is stronger emotionally and spiritually as compared to Anos. This, then, goes against the “natural” perception that men are stronger than women. This also affirms the idea that women play very important roles in the background as support system to the dominant and successful man that the public knows. Being the sole owner of a massive empire, Juan dela Cruz IV had expected his son to be like him: a lawyer, tycoon, and a womanizer. This is how men in the upper class are expected to be since they all have the money to burn on things they don’t even need, and society brushes this off. Men, being aggressive and dominant, are expected to accomplish assertive practices and hobbies by the society. So when Anos mentioned this to his father: “I know, Papa, that you want me to be a lawyer. I have been thinking about it. I’d like to be a poet” (142), Juan was very shocked. He expected more from Anos since he was the only one who would be inheriting the empire that he, together with his father and grandfather, created. It was a shocking revelation for Juan since Anos excelled in math and science – subjects that are associated with men – ever since he was in grade school, which is going to be a big help in the company. Literature and the arts have always been believed to be a very passive part of society, when in fact, it is an avenue of the most aggressive forms of retaliation and protest. Even so, the humanities is seen as passive that is why even Juan let go of his writing career. Anos broke his silence and insisted that he would want to be a poet, thus breaking the dominant stereotype by choosing a more “passive” course for college.

Aside from being the CEO of his own company, it is blatantly known to the audience that Juan dela Cruz IV is very virile and aggressive, not just at work, more so, in bed. He is aggressive in all the aspects of his life, and that is how he was trained by his father. Juan and his wife Bibi tried to have a baby for years, but failed. They both got checked and it was found out that Juan “was the one found inadequate. It was called Oligozoospermia: very few spermatozoa in his semen” (121). If one has this, it is more likely that one is infertile. This disorder is very hard to track because sexual and ejaculation function is normal, while it is only through lab activities that one would find out that he has a low sperm count. Impotence is one of the most common reasons for a man not to feel dominant. It may be the reason as to why Juan continued to be a sexual aggressor and a womanizer in order to compensate for his impotence. After so many years, he also probably wondered why among the different women he slept with, no one tried to contact him or go to him asking for child support which may in turn give him hints of his situation. Unlike his father, Juan dela Cruz III, Johnny had only two children in his lifetime, while his father had dozens of children from multiple women. Juan dela Cruz IV’s attitude of being aggressive may be to hide the fact that he is not as virile as most people would think of, in order for his subordinates and colleagues to still see him as a superior like his father.

Since Juan dela Cruz is the main character in the novel, it is just right that there are a lot of things to notice about him and around him. Juan dela Cruz IV’s relationship with the Leader is quite intriguing. Their relationship seems so deep to the point that:

The Leader had gifted him with a black bullet-proof Mercedes, one of the five ordered from Germany. Their favorite rendezvous was, of course, the bedroom of the Leader where they enjoyed all the privacy in the world. At times when he was there meeting with him, the Leader’s wife didn’t dare to come in” (84).

Juan dela Cruz IV’s relationship with the Leader may be associated to that of a homosocial relationship. A homosocial relationship, as Eve Sedgwick described it from *Between Men: English Literature and Male Homosocial Desire*, is:

Social bonds between persons of the same sex; it is a neologism, obviously formed by analogy with “homosexual,” and just as obviously meant to be distinguished from “homosexual.” In fact, it is applied to such activities as “male bonding,” which may, as in our society, be characterized by intense homophobia, fear and hatred of homosexuality (2435).

It is not very common that you meet a rich friend, or even a very rich relative that is very close to you, that is willing to buy an exclusive car for you. It is also the Leader who helped train the Juan to be who he is; the Leader is a very big part of who Juan has become. More than the material things, it is the fact that even the wife of the Leader is not powerful enough to meddle in the business of the two once they are inside the bedroom. The bedroom is also a very intimate place to stay in. It is very personal, not professional. That is why when it was mentioned that their favorite rendezvous was inside the bedroom, there were questions that came to mind, like “what were they doing inside?” “Why is there a need for all the privacy in the world?” and many others that may be connected to the skepticism of the relationship of the two. The intimacy of a bedroom is described in the following lines:

Ah, the bedroom where the most secret of secrets of the private man and official person could be unearthed. The bedroom – and certainly, Johnny knew only too well the Leader’s bedroom proclivities, too. For it was also he who often located the women the Leader lusted after – usually young Caucasians with fresh, pliant bodies, beauty queens if he could get them, because they were told in advance how ample their profit for a one-night fling or a weekend in the watering holes in Asia and the Continent, they gladly agreed (84).

The house of the Leader or Juan dela Cruz IV should be enough privacy for both of them to meet. It is not far off that their houses also have conference areas given the enormous lot that they own, so that should be enough privacy for both of them. The thing is, the “meeting” is brought inside the bedroom, where the most intimate of actions are done. It is a place of solitude and ease. One would not invite someone inside their bedrooms unless there is an intimate relationship or bond with that certain person. It is also interesting that it is Juan who would look for women for the Leader to hook up with. How would Juan be able to know the Leader’s preferences in bed, if he has not experienced it with the leader? Thus, this is

a very strong support to the statement that there is indeed an intimate relationship between the Leader and Juan, and this also coincides with Sedgwick's definition of homosocial desire as "the emerging pattern of male friendship mentorship, entitlement, rivalry, and hetero- and homosexuality was in an intimate and shifting relation to class; and that no element of that pattern can be understood outside of its relation to women and gender systems as a whole" (2434-2435).

It is important to take note that the characters are actually embodiments of their characterization in the novel. Nomenclature was utilized by Jose to add more color to the characters. Scientifically, nomenclature is the designation of all objects by name, which is very much how it is used in literature. In literature, nomenclature is when a writer uses names to build a foundation and further support the characterization of the character. Names itself serve as clues to the audience as to what the role or characterization of a character is. Almost all the characters used nomenclature to further elaborate each character's color.

Since F. Sionil Jose is an Ilocano, there are a lot of Ilocano nuances and terms that were used in the novel. The first and foremost character is Juan Bacnang and "bacnang meant someone affluent" (8), which was very ironic in Juan's childhood because they were poor as a church mouse. There were times, especially during drought, that they did not have food on the table, so Juan had to work extra hours at the field or find something else to do just to be able to get paid and buy something to eat, especially he stays with his mom and grandparents who are both very old. Juan and his family live in barrio Nalipatan, and Nalipatan in Ilocano means "forgotten." The barrio was most likely named as such because the things that happened in that certain barrio were things that Juan wanted to forget and suppress; although it is a big part of who he has become, it is something he is not proud of. Although he went there to visit several times, he never did say this story to his children. Ilocanos, aside from being frugal, are also very proud of their roots and this is one characteristic that Juan does not embody. Things that happened in barrio Nalipatan were, more often than not, about hardships of life. Juan grew up to be charming, but aside from that and him meeting Aning, – his true love – nothing else that was positive happened in Nalipatan.

The twins, Anos and Liwliwa, were named after Ilocano virtues. Anos "the Ilocano word for patience, the supreme virtue of his tribe, Anos, patience" (125), and Liwliwa "for someone who gave happiness" (126). Anos both did and did not embody this trait. He embodies patience during the time that his father sent him a prostitute for his 18th birthday.

On the one hand, Anos showcased patience and determination when, even if all the factors are present: privacy, a naked woman, her caressing his body, he still stood by his decision of not making any intimate contact with Jessica. On the other hand, he ran out of patience when he committed suicide; he was not patient enough to wait for his father to change, nor was he patient enough to wait for the wound to heal, a wound that was caused by the death of Jessica. Liw embodied the description of her name because she was the only one who made Anos happy after Jessica died, and after Anos died, Liw was also the only source of her father's happiness. Lastly, Jose also used nomenclature for the character of Mr. Tured, the journalist. Tured in Ilocano means "strong and brave," and in the novel, Mr. Narciso A. Tured, with the initials, N. A. Tured, or the word natured, showcased his willpower being strong and his bravery during the time that he was invited by Juan to lunch. In that fancy place, Mr. Tured knew very well that he was meeting with Juan dela Cruz IV, a close friend of the Leader and being friends, there must be an agenda to this unexpected invitation. Tured answered all Juan's question in a manner that made Juan a bit surprised because Juan did not expect the frankness of Tured. Tured also did not hold back at throwing shade to the Leader and his management of the country. Tured also strongly said that there is no way that he would be writing about The Leader in his column. Although Mr. Tured knew that his life might be at risk, he still continued to say what he wanted to say, trying to shed light into the dark business that the Leader and Juan were in. Tured died still writing about what he believed in, thus representing the strength and bravery of a real journalist.

The last point that this paper would point out is the similarity of Juan dela Cruz IV and the majority of the ethno-epic heroes tackled in the course. The ethno-epic hero is, more often than not, described as someone bigger than life, or someone that is extraordinary, as in different in a supernatural way. The ethno-epic hero saves the village or someone that is important – his father for instance. Much like the ethno-epic hero Lam-Ang in search for his father, Juan also had been searching for his father ever since he was small, but the stories he heard from his grandparents were enough. The moment Juan knew who his father was and was accepted by him, that is when Juan became someone larger than life. The wealth and power that was amassed by his father is out of this world. It seems so unreal that a barrio boy who hardly had food on his table suddenly had a corporation in a snap of a finger. This, then, is very surreal, much like the adventures of the ethno-epic heroes. Juan also is very blood thirsty; anyone who gets in his way or in the Leader's way, is to be killed. This trait is also seen in the ethno-epic heroes, as some battles would last for three years; three years of killing a tribe or a village. The character of Juan dela Cruz IV may be associated to the ethno-epic heroes because of merely a couple of similarities like: 1) Juan's wealth and power that is somewhat bigger than life; 2) the search for his father; and 3) the blood thirsty main character.

Conclusion

The novel expounds gravely on the value of the Filipino “macho” culture, but this paper explicated how gender roles were broken and how women served as valuable characters for the men in the novel to attain the success that they have. The reciprocation of power is also vividly described in the novel – how women drove one character to do a certain act – from men being dominant, women subordinate to women being more dominant and controlling, while men become more passive at women’s actions. Nomenclature also was tackled as it is one of the techniques that made the novel easier to read, and the association of the ethno-epic hero to the main character. No matter how subtle it may be, it is the female characters in the story that reigned and helped the male characters attain their achievements and cover up relationships that has to be hidden.

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